

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Understanding the impact of the socioeconomic crisis on the mental health and conflict management styles of the youth of the Western Province of Sri Lanka and its incite on migration: A comparison between current and past trends

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Abstract

This research investigates the socio-economic and psychosocial factors influencing youth decision-making and migration intentions in Sri Lanka, with a focus on the Western Province. The study contextualizes the challenges faced by the youth, exacerbated by the aftermath of the 2019 Easter attacks and the subsequent economic downturn intensified by the COVID-19 pandemic. Youth employment, educational opportunities, and the economic crisis are explored as contributors to distress levels and a potential motivation for migration. A Conflict Management Styles Assessment is incorporated to identify prevalent conflict resolution strategies among the youth. The findings reveal a significant relationship between socio-economic crises, mental health distress, and conflict resolution styles. The study emphasizes the need for effective conversation strategies, timely conflict resolution, and expert consultations. The observed distress levels and migration inclinations underscore the importance of addressing psychological well-being during crises, advocating for platforms enabling youth to voice concerns. The study recommends collaborative problem-solving approaches and highlights the essential role of mental health practitioners. Further research with larger sample sizes is proposed to validate and reinforce these findings, ensuring their applicability to broader youth demographics in Sri Lanka.

Keywords: Youth Migration; Sri Lanka; Socio-economic status; Conflict Management; Health and Well-being

1. Introduction

Post 2019 easter attacks in Sri Lanka, the public had gone through a series of changes which has negatively impacted their livelihoods and ways of living. As stated by Khan (2021), the role of “civil repair” had been a question in the minds of Sri Lankan citizens as they were looking at mitigation strategies to recover from the easter attacks. However, in 2020 a bigger threat emerged, where the COVID-19 pandemic caused a series of events to unfold and trigger an economic collapse in the country (Nandasena, 2021).

The manufacturing, tourism and agricultural sectors were affected mainly causing the demand for labour to decrease significantly resulting in several companies cutting down on staff to combat the crisis. Despite 2021 being a recovery year for most countries, Sri Lanka was facing a huge challenge of repaying debts to countries which resulted in limited imports and exports. Basic needs such as uninterrupted electricity supply, food supply and transportation services were

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limited due to this resulting in the uprising of the people's protest which led to a change in government leadership in the country (Mehta, 2022).

During this period of 3 years changes in the country, the youth had been significantly impacted due to the ongoing crisis and changes. Majority of the youth in the age group of 18-25 were either completing their high school certification, entering into universities or ending their university careers. As highlighted by Weerasiri (2021), limited investments made towards youth targeted job opportunities has caused a stirred reaction from the younger generation which provokes the thought of migration. Moreover, the free educational system policy results in only qualified students to go through to the university whilst the others end up searching for alternative means of survival (Alawattegama, 2020).

Based on our findings in the primary research, we identified that there is a significant relationship between socioeconomic crisis on the mental health among youth in Sri Lanka. This is backed by several countries carried in other countries such as Philippines, Indonesia and Malaysia where mental health implications cause a change in behaviour patterns of youth (Yeung & Yang, 2020). To ensure our studies identified potential conflict resolving mechanisms in times of crisis, a conflict management style questionnaire was adopted into the research based on Wang (2020) research.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Socioeconomic Outlook of Sri Lanka

Sri Lanka's economy was already showing signs of decline since 2019, where unstable monetary policies and floating exchange rates had contributed to external imbalances which is having a negative impact on growth and poverty. Sri Lanka defaulted on all its external debt of an estimated \$50 billion and declared bankruptcy in May 2022, the first time in history for the island nation. With one of the lowest tax-to-GDP ratios in the world due to the new tax cuts imposed by the government in 2019, Sri Lanka's credit rating had reduced significantly resulting in limited loans provided by international financial markets.

As stated by Warallavatte (2021), Sri Lankan employees who were working overseas had lost their jobs in large scale during the pandemic in 2020. Despite having limited job security overseas, many of them decided to stay back and find alternative ways of survival rather than returning to Sri Lanka. With the political instability created, foreign workers are discouraged to remit money to Sri Lanka.

Although the COVID-19 pandemic had impacted severe cash inflow through the tourism sector, Sri Lanka failed to adopt and adjust its monetary policies during 2020 resulting in the financial crisis (Dilukshie, 2021). Currently Sri Lanka faces a major challenge of holding their staff members in the country where both young adults and skilled professionals are moving into different countries which provides a significantly better salary (Ekanayake & Amirthalingam, 2020).

2.2. Role of Youth during the Crisis

The youth population also known as the next generation of workers are an essential component of success for any country. In Sri Lanka nearly 23.2% of the population comprises youth who are actively involved in various stages of the country's development. However, studies indicate that having a degree and technical expertise background is not sufficient to have a sustainable job in the country (Aboobucker, 2019).

Jayamaha (2022) in her research indicated that the youth uprising movement which resulted in the ousting of the government was predominantly a movement that signifies the power of the people in the country. Nearly 1/4th of the population in the country are between the ages of 18-30 which is the main stage of life for many individuals to build their own careers.

2.3. Bridging the gap between role of youth and socioeconomic outlook

To understand how socioeconomic factors influence the youth in the country, the research had indicated that migration, economical outlook and factors associated with the political instability had played a huge part in decision making. Based on the literature reviews carried out and the primary and secondary research findings obtained, the research decided to focus on three main dimensions. The impact of socioeconomic factors, mental health and conflict management styles.

3. Material and method

3.1. Design

The focus of this research was to increase youth participation by investigating the socio-economic and psychosocial factors such as the mental health (distress levels) and conflict management styles that influence young people's decision to leave Sri Lanka. The Western Province of Sri Lanka was chosen as the research's hub. The design employed, utilised quantitative methods. The closed ended questions used provided numbers which were subsequently analysed and interpreted through standard statistical procedures. To further give weight to the results obtained, a policy paper including the youth's participation and protection in relation to the country's migration laws was written, which was as per the final recommendations of the study.

3.2. Sample

Based on previous studies conducted and the literature review carried out, Western Province was chosen for recruitment as it constitutes more than 60% of Sri Lanka's youth population and it is considered as the commercial capital for education and employment. Further, it was identified that in the pre-economic crisis, the majority of the youth who were studying or were new employees, seek migratory options in Sri Lanka than older youth who have settled. Therefore, the target group of this study was youth within the age groups of 18-25 years.

Table 1 Population of youth in Colombo, Gampaha and Kalutara (the three districts of the Western Province (Sri Lanka population statistics, 2012)

	15-19	19-24	Total
Colombo	175,847	194,024	369,871
Gampaha	178,567	181,212	359,779
Kalutara	85,476	89,650	175,126
Total	439,890	464,886	904,776

Table 2 Calculation of the sample size (Sri Lanka population statistics, 2012)

Confidence level	95%
Margin of error	5%
Population proportion	50%
Population size	904,776
Sample size	384

3.3. Tools

Data were collected using an online survey questionnaire (Appendix 1) created through Google forms. It comprised three sections. The first section included a few screening questions and a demographic questionnaire which was utilised to collect details such as age, gender, educational qualification/s, employment status and socioeconomic status. The second section contained the GHQ12 (Montazeri *et al.*, 2003), and the third section contained the Conflict Management Styles Assessment. The questionnaires were translated to both the local languages (Sinhala and English) to ensure all participants understood the purpose of the research more concisely. The survey was disseminated among the participants via the application WhatsApp and email.

Following data collection, Microsoft Office Excel was employed for data cleaning and IBM SPSS Statistics v 25 software was utilised for data analysis, interpretation and validation.

3.4. Methodology

A comprehensive literature review using previous studies and surveys was conducted appertaining to the study. The knowledge acquired from this was utilised for the downstream activities in the study such as selection of the target group, the research proposal, execution of the data collection method and writing of the policy paper.

Thereafter, the closed ended questionnaire was made for data collection that comprised mainly of three sections. Section one primarily contained the demographic questions as mentioned above along with two questions that were used to understand the youth's perception on migration in the current economic status and whether migration could help their amelioration. The second section was designed to understand the mental health of the youth using their distress levels that have either increased, decreased or remained the same due to the ongoing economic crisis by utilising the GHQ12 as mentioned above. The third section's purpose was to recognize the trend in the conflict resolution styles of the youth in the present situation of Sri Lanka which ultimately affects youth security and their decision to migrate.

Dissemination of the survey began in late August 2022 and continued until the end of October 2022. It was distributed among the personal connections of the YAR team, numerous universities and companies and the community networks of UNESCO and PRIA.

Subsequently, during the data collection time period, a pilot study was conducted to identify the probable results and limitations of the study through how the survey was answered by the youth. Here it was recognized that the survey should include 'student' as an occupation in the demographic section and the predicted principles such as whether the economic status, mental health and conflict resolution styles affected the decision to migrate was validated. Afterwards, the final data were acquired, cleaned, analysed and interpreted to obtain the findings of the study. Finally, the findings were utilised to generate the policy paper which addressed the youth participation and protection during the current context of the economic crisis and their decision to migrate which revolves around the same context.

3.5. Data analysis

The data collected from participants were subjected to analysis using IBM SPSS statistics v 25 software. Initially, the data were transferred to a Microsoft Office Excel sheet to avoid disarray and the data in the Sinhala language were translated to the English language. Then it was transferred to an SPSS sheet as appropriate. Before the analysis, data cleaning was conducted. The entire data record of the participant was excluded from the data pool if missing data or an error was found. Following this, normality tests were carried out on scale data as per requirement which can be used to implicate the applicability of parametric or non-parametric tests based on data distribution. Descriptive statistics were drawn to understand the sample population. A regression analysis was carried out to determine the relationship between the scores of the GHQ12 and conflict resolution styles and the decision to migrate.

3.6. Ethics

A consent form (https://docs.google.com/document/d/1_o1aoxEa8AmTTYtiZJKuWjxze52cM2OrF0sAq1HeTVM/edit) and information sheet (<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1fmzWe6CFy1dHlap0SSjgzQSB0qj4gXb0/edit>) were included at the beginning of the questionnaire disclosing a data confidentiality clause which safeguarded the information provided by the participant with the expectation that it was not to be used for any other purpose other than this research.

Access to the survey questionnaire has only been available to the research team members and all files and folders were password protected with encryption. Once the research is over all the data will be handed over to UNESCO and all the personally identifiable data of respondents/participants will be deleted from our devices.

There were no significant questions that were to cause any discomfort or distress among the participants as all the questions were streamlined as general questions. If in any case a participant felt uncomfortable responding to the questionnaire, she/he/they could withdraw at any given moment after informing the research team.

Limitations

The sample size of 384 participants were not reached as only 105 participants provided consent. As a result, even though it was proposed that qualitative data were to be collected through online focus group discussions and interviews, they were not conducted. Furthermore, a highly diverse demographic was not noticed among the participants as many of the respondents were representing either one or two of the vastly available categories.

To overcome these limitations, the number of participants should increase with greater dissemination of the survey among the said target group in the Western province of Sri Lanka.

4. Result and discussion

For the study we used an online questionnaire to gather responses for the research where 105 people have provided consent for the data to be analyzed for this research. 75% of the data received are female and 25% are male.

Considering the age levels, 18-year-olds are 2%, 20-year-olds are 2%. 29-year-olds 29%, 22-years-old 23%, 23-years-old 5%, 24-years-old 12% and 25-years-old 27%. According to the married and unmarried status, 13% of married people and 87% of unmarried people have been given data.

When classifying the people who provided data according to ethnicity, 97% represented the Sinhalese and 2% represented the Moor. A group of 1% have introduced their ethnicity as Sri Lankans. In terms of religion, 88% are Buddhists, 6% are Christians, and 2% are Muslims. Athesis 1%, Hindus 1%, Roman Catholics 1% and 1% who have no religion are given data. In the analysis of the education level of the data given group, 2% of the people who have completed their education up to the Ordinary level are 2%.

33% of the people who have studied up to Advanced Level. 9% of the people who have studied up to the diploma level, 59% of the people who have studied up to the degree level. 1% of the people who have studied up to postgraduate degrees. 2 in the armed forces and 1 in clerical while classifying according to the job done. Craft related trade 2. Elementary 1, Manager 8, Professionals 45. service and sales 4. Skilled Agriculture 1. Student is 31. 9 technicians and others.

In the study of how they get paid, there are 14 people who get paid daily. 86 per month. Two are paid seasonally and two are paid weekly. When sorting by monthly income. There are 8 people who earn more than one lakh rupees. There are 36 people who receive less than thirty thousand loves. There are 27 people who earn between 30000-49999 rupees. There are 15 people who earn between 50000-69999 rupees. There are 18 people who earn between 70000 and 100000 rupees.

4.1. The idea of leaving the country

Figure 1 Perception of Individuals on leaving country

66% of the people who gave the data stated that they intend to leave the country in the near future. It represents a greater majority overall. 27% said that they do not have a definite idea yet and only 7% said that they have no intention of leaving the country at the moment. What is clear from this data is that most of the youth community are hoping to leave Sri Lanka. Only a very small number aspires to stay in Sri Lanka.

According to the current situation in Sri Lanka, the attitude that one should migrate in order to succeed in their future

Figure 2 Youth Perception on Leaving Sri Lanka

According to the data, 92 percent believe that they should migrate for their future and career success. Only 8% say no. According to the aforementioned data, a large percentage of the 27% who currently have no intention of going abroad have confidence that the future will be successful if they migrate. This data shows that most of the youth community in the country believe that their future will not be successful by living in the country.

4.2. The General Health Questionnaire

The General Health Questionnaire (GHQ-12) was used to assess the psychological well-being in participants on a 4 point likert scale. Higher scores indicate psychological distress.

According to the results, the majority of the participants are distressed in a range of mild to severe (57%). The overall results indicate an association between the ideation of participants to leave the country to succeed in the future and distress experienced during the economic crisis.

The analysis for each item of the GHQ and the overall scores of the sample are as follows.

4.2.1. Been able to concentrate on what you were doing?

Figure 3 Individual Focus and Concentration Patterns of Individuals

56% of people say that they are doing the same as usual. 22% that they are at less than usual. 14% have commented that they are doing better than usual and 8% as Much than usual.

4.2.2. *Lost much sleep over worry?*

Figure 4 Health and sleep of Individuals affected by external factors

No more than usual and rather than usual answers given 33% respectively. 27% said not at all and 7% said much more than usual.

4.2.3. *Felt you were playing a useful part in things?*

Figure 5 Participant Reflections on Perceived Impact whether individuals felt they were playing a meaningful role in contributing to positive outcomes.

65% said the same as usual. The amount declared as more than usual is 15%. The amount declared as less than usual is 11%. 9% of the people declared as much less capable.

4.2.4. *Felt capable of making decisions about things?*

Figure 6 Participants' self-perceptions on their capability to make informed decisions

58% responded the same as usual. 21% said more than usual. 16% responded as usual. 5% responded as much less than usual.

4.2.5. *Felt constantly under strain?*

Figure 7 Representation of participants' reported experiences of continuous stress

The responses received for this are scattered responses. In no case did the response exceed 50%. 31% responded as rather usual. 30% responded as not at all. 25% responded as no more than usual. 14% responded much more than usual.

4.2.6. *Felt you couldn't overcome your difficulties?*

Figure 8 Challenges overcoming difficulties

37% responded NOT at all. 27% responded as no more than usual. 23% responded rather more than usual. 13% responded much more than usual.

4.2.7. *Been able to enjoy your normal day-to-day activities?*

Figure 9 Day to day living conditions and activities

53% answered same as usual. 23% answered as less useful than usual. 15% answered as much less than usual and 9% answered as more than usual.

4.2.8. *Been able to face up to your problems?*

Figure 10 Overcoming challenges by facing problems

49% said same as usual. 23% responded as more than usual. 19% responded as less useful than usual and 9% as much less than usual.

4.2.9. *Been feeling unhappy and depressed?*

Figure 11 Personal feelings indicated that people have feelings of being unhappy and depressed

35% responded as No More than Usual. 26% responded that More than Usual. 24% said not at all and 15% said Much more than usual.

4.2.10. *Been losing confidence in yourself?*

Figure 12 Confidence Level Indicator

37% as no more than usual and 29% as not at all. 27% as rather more than usual. 7% commented as much more than usual.

4.2.11. *Been thinking of yourself as a worthless person?*

Figure 13 Self thoughts and decision making

56% as NOT at all and 19% as no more than usual. 13% much more than usual. 12% commented rather than usual.

4.2.12. *Been feeling reasonably happy, all things considered*

Figure 14 Feelings Indicator

54% about the same as usual. 30% less useful than usual. 11% said more so than usual and 5% said much less than usual.

4.2.13. *GHQ total*

Figure 15 GHQ Questionnaire Total Score of all Participants

4.2.14. Stress Level

Figure 16 Stress Level Indicator

4.3. The conflict management style questionnaire

The conflict management style questionnaire was utilized as a part of the solution process which aimed to guide the youth in their journey to making sustainable decisions that positively impact their decisions on migration. The analysis below shows the thought process behind the conclusion at which we have deduced. The main conflict management styles that were focused upon were:

- Collaborating (Questions 1,5,7)
- Accommodating (Questions 3,11,14)
- Compromising (Questions 2,8,13)
- Avoiding (Questions 6,10,15)
- Competing (Questions 4,9,12)

As stated, the 15 statements correspond to the five conflict management styles. The style with the highest score indicates the most commonly used strategy. The one with the lowest score indicates the least preferred strategy. However, all styles have pros and cons, so it's important that one uses the most appropriate style for each conflict situation.

4.4. I discuss issues with others to try to find solutions that meet everyone's needs

It is understood that in terms of discussing issues to accommodate everyone's needs, more of than not, our respondents have been engaging in discussion to ensure that when making a decision and/or when solving their problems with regards to migration, they tend to take decisions on a "solution fits all" basis. Majority of them (39%) take into account what those around them think of the decision as opposed to the 8% who rarely do so.

Figure 17 Majority (39%) engage in 'solution fits all' discussions, prioritizing decisions that consider everyone's needs, while 8% rarely take into account others' opinions

4.5. I try to negotiate and use a give-and-take approach to problem situations

Figure 18 Recognizing the influence of family bonds, 38% of youth are open to healthy compromise, aligning decisions with both personal needs and family expectations in migration choices

While understanding that our respondents are also those within the youth category, it is evident that they would try to make decisions that fit the needs of themselves as well as their parents and/or close family due to the nature of bonds in the Sri Lanka context. On that note, we can see that in a sense 38% of them are willing to engage in healthy compromise when considering their decisions of migrating to another country.

4.6. I try to meet the expectations of others

With the understanding of the fact that a majority of our respondents to try to compromise and accommodate as much of the needs of those around them, it is not a surprise to note that a majority of their conflict management and/or decision making process includes 42% of them wanting to meet the expectations of others in terms of country/region they want to fly to as well as study/work programmes to enroll in.

Figure 19 2% of respondents, in their conflict management and decision-making process, prioritize meeting the expectations of others in terms of destination and study/work programs

4.7. I would argue my case and insist on the advantages of my point of view

Figure 20 Contrary to traditional cultural norms, 34% of respondents assert their career and educational preferences, gaining a competitive advantage in decision-making

Culturally, what is understood within the community within Sri Lanka is that, what the parents/adults say goes but it is quite eye opening that the majority of our youth respondents (34%) are willing and able to understand what helps their career, studies and futures and are able to speak up on that regard and gain a competitive advantage.

4.8. When there is a disagreement, I gather as much information as I can and keep the lines of communication open

46% of our youth respondents are making more informed decisions by trying to come to decisions that would benefit them as seen in the above graph and it is very important to note that it is not an authoritative route that they take but a more democratic and accommodating one.

Figure 21 6% of youth prioritize democratic and accommodating routes, emphasizing collaborative approaches in the decision-making process

4.9. When I find myself in an argument, I usually say very little and try to leave as soon as possible

Figure 22 Indicating that 49% of respondents opt to walk out of discussions to gather thoughts or collect more information.

This criteria correlates with the previous question/criteria which shows that in order to avoid major conflicts/disagreements that 49% of these respondents would walk out of discussions to either gather their thoughts, collect more information or process the facts of the decision to make a more informed decision.

4.10. I try to see conflicts from both sides. What do I need? What does the other person need? What are the issues involved?

When making decisions, especially those with regards to one's future, it is important to understand how it affects each and everyone that are close to those that are making such decisions. These youth decision makers are collaborative in

that sense as 39% of our respondents take into account all aspects of the decision in order to drive a successful negotiation process.

Figure 23 39% consider all aspects, driving successful negotiations

4.11. I prefer to compromise when solving problems and just move on

Figure 24 39% lean towards compromise in collaborative decision-making

Although the concept of compromising is a tricky one, we can see that 39% of our respondents are more inclined towards compromising since the trend in decision making so far or conflict management is leaning towards including those all around them as opposed to a singular decision making process.

4.12. I find conflicts exhilarating; I enjoy the battle of wits that usually follows

Figure 25 Diverse opinions make conflicts unavoidable in the win-win decision process

It is a given in any context that conflicts are draining and anyone would prefer avoiding such conflicts. However, conflicts are inevitable due to the fact that people have diverse opinions and when making a win-win decision, it is part and parcel of the process.

4.13. Being in a disagreement with other people makes me feel uncomfortable and anxious

Figure 26 50% of respondents occasionally feel uneasy in disagreements

Being in conflict or disagreement with those around you more often than not brings around a sense of discomfort. However, as per the responses, it is evident it has been divided into a 50-50 situation where 50% (majority) of our respondents sometimes feel uncomfortable when in disagreement.

4.14. I try to meet the wishes of my friends and family

Figure 27 Illustrating the prevalence of collaboration, with 41% of respondents frequently prioritizing the desires of friends and family.

Following the trend of collaborating when making decisions we can see that a majority of 41% are often inclined towards meeting the wishes of friends and family considering that they are immediate internal factors that often impact the decision-making process of youth.

4.15. I can figure out what needs to be done and I am usually right

Figure 28 Highlighting that 50% of surveyed youth exhibit proactive awareness and strategic planning, having analyzed a comprehensive array of options through consultations and online/offline information sources

50% of the youth as per the survey are aware & in tune with what they need for their future and have analyzed most or all available options for their future based on consultations and/or available information online/offline.

4.16. To break deadlocks, I would meet people halfway

Figure 29 Illustrating that 45% of participants are inclined towards resolving deadlocks by either retracing steps or engaging in compromise, showcasing a prevalent adaptive approach to challenging impasses

Deadlocks are usually tricky situations to be in considering that often there is no way forward from such situations. However, in order to get out of it, it is important to either trace your steps backwards and/or try to start compromising which is what the majority (45%) of our respondents are willing to do.

4.17. I may not get what I want but it's a small price to pay for keeping the peace

Figure 30 Our findings indicate that 41% of respondents are inclined towards creating an accommodating/compromising situation, emphasizing a willingness to invest effort and resources to ensure a process that is minimally exhausting and maximally fruitful.

Decision making/conflict management is about ensuring all parties involved are treated fairly & equally. In order to do so, one needs to create an accommodating/compromising situation which is what 41% of our respondents are willing to pay to ensure that the process is the least exhausting and most fruitful.

4.18. I avoid hard feelings by keeping my disagreements with others to myself

Figure 31 A significant 43% of respondents tend to internalize their disagreements as a strategy to minimize conflict.

In order to avoid as much conflict as possible, 43% of our respondents often keep their disagreements to themselves. However we can also see that a close 34% do voice out their disagreements always which can be considered either in an aggressive sense or as a defence mechanism to prove that they do have decision making skills.

4.19. Collaborating

Figure 32 Collaboration Management Style Representation - Accounting for 21.4% of the respondents, individuals employing the collaboration technique are commonly associated with 'owl' personalities

Whilst 21.4% of the respondents belonged to this management style, Those who follow a collaboration technique are often deemed as owl personalities. They see conflict as a problem to be solved, and they seek a solution that achieves both their goals and the goals of the other person. Owls see conflicts as a way to improve relationships by reducing tensions between two people. They attempt to start a discussion that identifies the conflict as a problem, and they strive to resolve tensions and maintain the relationship by seeking solutions that satisfy both themselves and the other person.

4.20. Competition

Figure 33 Competing Management Style Representation - Constituting 17.9% of the respondents, individuals adopting the competing technique are commonly associated with 'shark' personalities.

Whilst 17.9% of the respondents belonged to this management style, Those who follow a competing technique are often deemed as shark personalities. Sharks typically prioritize their goals over their relationships, which means that if forced to choose, they would prioritize their goals over their relationships. Sharks are usually more concerned with achieving their objectives than with being liked by others. They may attempt to overpower opponents in order to force them to accept their conflict resolution.

4.21. Avoiding

Figure 34 Avoiding Management Style Representation - Comprising 19.2% of the respondents, individuals employing the avoiding technique are commonly associated with 'turtle' personalities.

Whilst 19.2% of the respondents belonged to this management style, Those who follow an avoiding technique are often deemed as turtle personalities. Turtles prioritize avoiding conflict over either their goals or their relationships. They frequently find it easier to avoid a conflict than to confront it. This may even imply giving up all their relationships or goals associated with the conflict.

4.22. Accommodating

Figure 35 Accommodating Management Style Representation - Constituting 20.7% of the respondents, individuals adopting the accommodating technique are often associated with 'teddy bear' personalities.

Whilst 20.7% of the respondents belonged to this management style, Those who follow an accommodating technique are often deemed as teddy bear personalities. These personalities typically prioritize relationships over their own goals; if forced to choose, Teddy Bears will frequently sacrifice their goals to maintain relationships. Teddy Bears generally want to be liked by others and avoid conflict because they believe it will harm relationships. Teddy Bears attempt to smooth over conflict in order to protect the relationship.

4.23. Compromising

Figure 36 Compromising Management Style Representation - Among the respondents, 20.2% adopt the compromising technique, commonly associated with 'fox' personalities.

Whilst 20.2% of the respondents belonged to this management style, Those who follow a compromising technique are often deemed as fox personalities. Foxes are moderately concerned with their goals and their interpersonal relationships. Foxes typically seek a compromise; they give up some of their goals in order to persuade the other person in a conflict to give up some of their goals. They seek a conflict resolution in which both parties benefit; a happy medium between two extreme positions. They are willing to give up some of their objectives in order to reach a consensus for the greater good.

4.24. CR type Conclusion

Figure 37 Analysis of responses reveals a prevalent inclination toward collaboration among youth when navigating migration decisions.

In the examination of inquiries aimed at elucidating the conflict management styles among youth concerning their decision-making process regarding migration, the prevailing inclination is toward collaboration. The findings suggest that participants favor a harmonious equilibrium, prioritizing the sustenance of personal relationships while concurrently charting a course toward realizing their migration objectives.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the predominant Conflict Resolution type suggests that a considerable portion of the youth is still in the decision-making phase, with the influence of those around them playing a pivotal role. To enhance this process, implementing a strategic approach to conversation becomes crucial, recognizing the time and energy investments associated with collaborative decision-making and conflict management, given the involvement of multiple individuals in the decision-making process. Establishing such practices can mitigate the likelihood of numerous contradictions or disagreements simply through effective communication.

Additionally, addressing disagreements promptly by taking time for information gathering or consulting professionals is recommended. This ensures that decisions are made sustainably and with greater effectiveness, benefitting from expert opinions rather than relying solely on less experienced perspectives. The observed higher distress levels and the prevalent inclination to migrate for a better future underscore the potential impact of the country's economic crisis on participants' decisions to leave. This finding underscores the imperative of addressing psychological well-being during crises, advocating for platforms that empower youth to express genuine concerns about their future and reasons for emigration. Such platforms offer a strategic means to alleviate stress and provide an opportunity for youth to build networks with peers facing similar challenges. Consequently, addressing specific issues arising from the economic crisis can be approached collaboratively, leveraging diverse perspectives within a team.

Furthermore, the demonstrated need for mental health practitioners to contribute to addressing high emigration rates during crises highlights the significant role these professionals can play in addressing broader societal challenges tied to psychological well-being and migration decisions. Moving forward, it is recommended that further studies be conducted with larger sample sizes to validate these findings, ensuring the robustness of conclusions drawn from this research.

Recommendations

- Implement Communication Strategies

Establish effective conversation strategies to facilitate collaborative decision-making, recognizing the time and energy involved in managing conflicts within the decision-making process.

- Address Disagreements Promptly

Encourage the resolution of disagreements in real-time by either taking a pause to gather more information or consulting professionals. This ensures sustainable and effective decision-making with the guidance of expert opinions.

- Prioritize Psychological Well-being

Recognize the impact of psychological well-being on decision-making, particularly during crises. Create platforms that enable youth to express genuine concerns about their future, fostering stress alleviation and opportunities for building networks with peers facing similar challenges.

- Promote Collaborative Problem-Solving

Emphasize collaborative approaches to addressing specific issues arising from the economic crisis. Leverage diverse perspectives within a team to develop comprehensive solutions.

- Engage Mental Health Practitioners

Acknowledge the crucial role of mental health practitioners in addressing high emigration rates during crises. Encourage their active contribution to societal challenges related to psychological well-being and migration decisions.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

The present research work does not contain any studies performed on animals/humans subjects by any of the authors.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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Appendices

Appendix I: Questionnaire

<https://forms.gle/qvST6m6oN3RCDLzb8>

Appendix II: Raw results obtained from the survey

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1uckoYMxKcjVW8pUBqBDQSLQ9jkYjYlgtpprQZubeXY/edit#gid=438298303>